

In situ decommissioning of subsea infrastructure

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Abstract: From an engineering and ecological perspective is it more rational to leave offshore oil and gas infrastructure in situ after decommissioning? This paper addresses that question. Options for decommissioning offshore infrastructure are set out. The emphasis of this paper is decommissioning of subsea infrastructure, which comprise a large proportion of current oil and gas offshore infrastructure, and an increasing proportion of total offshore assets in the future. This is due to the global trend towards multi-field developments tied back to a host platform or directly to shore, or to a floating LNG production platform. Potential challenges associated with retrieval of subsea structures and pipelines, and their long term stability, are considered from a geotechnical perspective. Viewed through the lens of in situ decommissioning, the evidence of a general long term rise in bearing capacity and stability indicates potential for infrastructure to have a safe and valuable post-operational afterlife as part of the marine ecosystem.

1 Introduction

A variety of infrastructure has been built in our oceans to harness and transport oil and gas from reservoirs deep beneath the ocean floor to onshore processing plants. Globally, this offshore infrastructure amounts to tens of thousands of wells, thousands of platforms and a range of seabed structures including many thousands of kilometres of pipeline. Much offshore oil and gas infrastructure has been in service for several decades and is approaching retirement as fields cease to be economical to produce with the current infrastructure. For example, over 550 platforms and subsea production facilities are situated in the North Sea, a mere 7% of which have been decommissioned to date and much is forecast for the coming three decades (Royal Academy of Engineering, 2013), while South East Asia hosts close to 1700 offshore installations, nearly half of which are older than 20 years and are due to be retired (NUS, 2013).

Following decommissioning, including cleaning oil, gas and residues from the system, the options include (1) complete removal of infrastructure; (2) partial removal and relocation of remaining infrastructure to another offshore site; (3) partial removal with the remaining infrastructure left in place (in situ); or (4) a combination of (1), (2) and (3). These potential options are illustrated schematically in Figure 1 along with a prospective option for augmenting remaining infrastructure with purpose-engineered artificial reefs. The choice depends on what is legally permissible and technically feasible, and also what is desirable from an environmental, economic and societal perspective.

Figure 1: Decommissioning options

Considering option (1) complete removal: Technical challenges faced when removing offshore infrastructure from the oceans include how to safely recover these ageing and often vast structures from harsh environments and what to do with them when they are brought to shore. Some parts of the topsides of platforms may be refurbished and redeployed if structurally sound.

An example of this approach is the recommissioning of the Conoco-operated Hutton Tension Leg Platform topsides on the Gazprom-operated Pirazlomniya platform. This second life gives the topside two unique claims: it was both the first tension leg platform and also the first commercial arctic production platform. However, this example is an uncommon practice, and much of the volume of offshore infrastructure is not reusable and while elements can be recycled much ends up in landfill.

From an engineering perspective, complete removal poses challenges that will be discussed throughout this conference, but these challenges can generally be overcome with sufficient investment. The offshore industry has an established track record of developing technology to engineer solutions for installation and operation of offshore facilities of extreme scale and in extreme environments, and it is now turning its efforts towards decommissioning – for example, the *Pioneering Spirit*, the specialised vessel constructed to lift steel platforms from the North Sea (<http://allseas.com/equipment/pioneering-spirit/>). The development of these technologies has been driven by the underlying legal requirement to remove abandoned infrastructure (OSPAR 1998), but this may not necessarily be the most appropriate solution.

Considering option (2) partial removal and relocation of remaining infrastructure to another offshore site: This decommissioning option is most well-known through the rigs-to-reef program administered through the US Bureau of Safety and Environmental Enforcement (<http://www.bsee.gov/>). The establishment of this program led to steel jacket structures being toppled or moved and left in situ, where they form reefs, contributing both to marine habitat and serving as a recreational fishery. The potential role of oil and gas infrastructure as habitat for marine biota is a major driving force for the 'rigs-to-reefs' debate and policy changes that provide for partial removal (Claisse et al., (2014), Macreadie et al., (2011)). Current rigs-to-reefs options often involve relocating the rig to a new site, and over 400 decommissioned rigs have been converted to permanent reefs since the start of the program in 1986. The rigs-to-reefs approach, as practiced in the US, generally involves removing the rig from the initial site and relocating it with other decommissioned rigs at a common location. This may not maximise the environmental benefits if the established ecosystem formed around the structure is disturbed (Figure 2). There are also technical challenges and expense involved in the relocation process. The programme has also focused on the steel jacket structure and not to the variety of subsea infrastructure increasingly associated with offshore oil and gas developments.

Figure 2: Established marine ecosystems around offshore oil and gas infrastructure (Figures adapted from Leckie et al., 2015; Leckie et al., 2016c)

There are engineering challenges and potential consequences for the marine ecology with removal and relocation of infrastructure. The question can therefore be asked: from an engineering and ecological perspective is it more rational to leave offshore infrastructure in situ after decommissioning, i.e. option (3), in situ decommissioning? This option is explored, from a geotechnical perspective, in this paper. Multi and inter-disciplinary considerations of in situ (and other) decommissioning options being considered by the authors and colleagues are presented in e.g. Techera & Chandler (2015), Gourvenec & Techera (2016) and Chandler et al. (2016). In practice, a suitably nimble policy framework enabling a combination of options 1, 2 and 3 is likely to provide the best solution for all stakeholders and ocean resources, whether commercial or recreational users, or the marine flora and fauna.

This paper is the opening keynote presentation of the Conference on Maritime Energy: Decommissioning of Offshore Geotechnical Structures, which brings together participants from a range of disciplines, both inside and outside of the offshore energy industry. Given this audience and context, we present in this paper a combination of material that offers both an overview of the multi-disciplinary decommissioning challenge – sharing our Australian perspective – as well as specific recent geotechnical research that sheds light on some of the engineering aspects of decommissioning subsea structures. The structure of the paper is as follows:

- The high-level motivation for, and considerations of, in situ decommissioning are first presented, including clarification of the intention of the term “in situ decommissioning” as used in this paper (Section 2).
- An overview of decommissioning issues in an Australian context is then outlined, considering the scale and maturity of our oil and gas industries and our particular ocean environment (Section 3).
- The range of subsea infrastructure that may require decommissioning and consideration of the scale and volume of these structures are then presented (Section 4).
- A focus is then placed on the engineering of decommissioning, discussing how conventional design approaches for new and life extended infrastructure may be recast to assess the feasibility of in situ decommissioning (Section 5).
- We then summarise some recent research outcomes addressing geotechnical aspects of decommissioning – that of recovery loads or the in-place stability of infrastructure that is decommissioned in situ (Sections 6 and 7).
- A final section considers augmentation of locations with in situ decommissioned offshore oil and gas infrastructure with purpose-engineered artificial reefs to optimise the enhancement to the marine ecosystem (Section 8).

2 In situ decommissioning

If the cost and risk associated with engineered removal are to be eliminated, the alternative must be demonstrated to be safe from an engineering and ecological perspective.

Evidence indicates that artificial reefs can form around offshore structures and their removal would end the ecosystem services the structures provide. Indeed engineered structures are often intentionally placed in our oceans to form artificial reefs for fisheries and tourism. These structures provide established habitats for marine life and prime sites for recreational fishing and diving. Decommissioned structures could also be used for this purpose in various contexts.

Furthermore, the costs of a total removal policy may not be warranted - such as the financial and environmental cost of removal and the impact of disposal when the infrastructure is brought onshore, as highlighted above. The financial cost is borne both by operators and owners of the facilities, and also by the taxpayer in most jurisdictions, given the tax structures in place associated with decommissioning activities.

In situ decommissioning in the context of this paper means leaving offshore infrastructure in its original location, potentially adding additional engineered structures to the area to further boost the marine ecosystem. This is in contrast to removal and relocation, as often adopted in rigs-to-reef projects. The same science and evidence base applies to the whole spectrum of options, but this paper places an emphasis on the whole-life response of subsea infrastructure that may increase its stability – and also preserve the established marine ecosystem that has developed around the infrastructure. In contrast, removal (even for relocation) could be difficult and do more harm than good.

The following sections provide the Australian context then examine some of the engineering considerations related to in situ decommissioning with a focus on subsea infrastructure.

3 Australian context

The oceans around Australia, and in particular off the North West coast where the majority of the oil and gas facilities are sited, are a pristine region relatively untouched by human development until the past 200 years. This region of ocean is home to an ecosystem that includes habitats of high ecological value including mangroves, seagrass, coral and sponges. These habitats support a diverse fish population as well as rare species such as dugongs, turtles and whale sharks (CSIRO, 2007). Meanwhile, the ecosystem services fishing, shipping and recreational use.

The Australian offshore oil and gas industry began with platforms installed in Bass Strait in the late 1960s, and in the early 1980s the Woodside-operated North West Shelf Venture opened up development off the North West coast. Since then, more than 30 projects have entered production, with an intensive growth period in the last decade. These include large gas projects feeding onshore liquefied natural gas (LNG) plants and smaller oil projects connected to onshore processing or floating production units. The Prelude floating liquefied natural gas (FLNG) facility is shortly to arrive, heralding a new era of offshore LNG production.

A small number of these earliest projects have already been decommissioned, including the Jabiru and Challis FPSO developments (Wright, 2015). In this case a mixture of in situ decommissioning and removal was adopted. A wave of further decommissioning lies ahead, as illustrated by the project timelines shown in Figure 3. A 2005 study of Australian offshore decommissioning yielded an estimated total cost of ~\$1B at that time (O'Neill et al., 2005). Subsequent growth of the industry has led to an increase in this liability, which is currently estimated to be ~US\$21Bn (~€20Bn) (NERA, 2016). An emergent focus among the operators, other stakeholders and the research community is the relevant knowledge needed to guide and optimise the decommissioning strategy for these projects.

The total number of projects in Australia is low relative to more mature regions of development such as the North Sea. However, many of the Australian projects are large scale – particularly those supporting onshore LNG plants – and together represent an investment of > \$100B over

the past decade. For example, the Ichthys project involves two large floating facilities anchored by 49 large diameter piles, more than 20 subsea structures, several infield pipelines and an export pipeline that is almost 900 km in length (www.inpex.com.au).

Figure 3: Expected operational life of selected Western Australian offshore oil and gas projects (WAMSI, 2015)

4 Subsea infrastructure

Subsea infrastructure encapsulates a variety of structures installed on or in the seabed that do not break the waterline. A selection of subsea infrastructure is illustrated schematically in Figure 4. Subsea infrastructure that requires decommissioning when a field becomes unviable includes a range of facilities such as:

- Subsea equipment (e.g. compressors, separators) and supporting structures (e.g. manifolds, pipe terminations, in-line structures, buckle initiators).
- Pipelines (e.g. export pipelines, infield flowlines, spools, jumpers).
- Ancillary facilities (e.g. concrete mattresses, rock blankets).

Subsea equipment is typically founded on mudmats, shallow foundations, which may be augmented with deeper foundation elements such as suction caissons or piles. Subsea pipeline infrastructure, such as manifolds, pipe terminations, in-line structures or buckle initiators, support the in-field pipeline network. Edge lengths of foundations for subsea structures typically lie in the range of 5 m – 20 m. However, the largest subsea structures in the world include the Asgard subsea compression unit, with a footprint 75 m by 45 m and mass of nearly 5000 t and the Jansz manifold, with a footprint of 30 m by 40 m and mass of 2000 t. These large subsea structures required specialised heavy lifting vessels and equipment to install them and can be forecast to require technology innovations to remove them from the seabed at the end of field life. A photograph of a typical pipeline end manifold structure supported on a shallow skirted foundation, or mudmat, is shown in Figure 5.

Infield pipelines transmit hydrocarbons from a network of wells to a single production facility while export pipelines send oil and gas to shore. In-field flow-lines are typically 6 – 18 inches

(0.15 – 0.45 m) in diameter and may form networks of many tens of kilometres in a subsea development carrying hydrocarbons from wells to processing facilities and chemicals for injection along the system. Export pipelines can be up to 42 inches (1.06 m) in diameter and stretch for hundreds of kilometres. There are also umbilical cables for the provision of electrical and hydraulic power as well as communication via wire or fibre. Other short lengths of pipeline called spools or jumpers are used to connect subsea facilities.

Figure 4: Schematic of selection of subsea structures

Figure 5: Pipeline end manifold structure on skirted mudmat

Additional structures placed at the seabed include heavy concrete mattresses, rocks transported from land or other dense structures that are placed on pipelines to improve stability. Various types of structure are also placed on pipeline routes to create undulations that ease the relief of thermal expansion. A recent decommissioning plan from a small North Sea project (Endeavour, 2013) reveals detailed arrangements to recover 250 segmented concrete mattresses, each weighing ~ 4 tonnes, for disposal in an onshore landfill site.

The volume of subsea infrastructure is vast when considering removal and disposal, with potentially many tens of subsea structures and hundreds of kilometres of infield and export pipelines in a single project. While decommissioning steel and concrete fixed platforms are high-profile and high-cost individual projects to attract attention, the volume of subsea infrastructure, including pipelines, will potentially require a significant proportion of the overall cost of decommissioning (e.g. Arup, 2014, Oil & Gas UK, 2013).

While subsea infrastructure is varied and covers multiple scales of size and complexity, in all cases, it is necessary to mobilise vessels and crew into a hazardous environment to perform these recoveries, and there are significant financial costs involved.

This paper explores how the response of the seabed and marine environment over the whole-life of the development may make retrieval harder than initially anticipated, which can be translated as an increase in stability if viewed through the lens of in situ decommissioning.

5 Design basis for the after-life

If infrastructure is to be left in situ, or relocated and left in the ocean, it must be acceptably engineered for this ‘afterlife’. The engineering rationale for the post-decommissioned afterlife is somewhat different compared to the initial operational design life, when the infrastructure is part of a field that is producing hydrocarbons. The engineering ‘design’ for in situ decommissioning requires that the structure is sufficiently stable on the seabed such that there will not be dispersal of the structure – in either large or small parts – that creates either unwanted environmental impact or a hazard to shipping. In contrast, during the initial operating life, the design criteria are more stringent: tighter criteria govern the allowable movements or deformations of structures and pipelines and the required margin against failure.

Conventional engineering design assessments in the oil and gas industry are predicated on a risk profile associated with the presence of hydrocarbons that have the potential to cause explosive damage and environmental harm, often in close proximity to temporary or permanently stationed personnel. Given the high potential consequences of an unwanted event, the design point is chosen to ensure an extremely low event probability, in order that the total risk is acceptable.

For oil and gas facilities that have undergone in situ decommissioning or have been decommissioned and relocated to another offshore site, the engineering integrity of the infrastructure post-decommissioning should be assessed using a different engineering assessment, because the associated risk profile is very different. There is no longer the presence of hydrocarbons – assuming well abandonment and facility purging has been performed correctly – and there are no personnel remaining on a platform (unless the post-decommissioning use involves transformation into, for example, a recreational facility).

The transformed risk profile means that engineering design assessments require recalibration, for example to revisit the ‘safety factors’ that contribute to the margin between the design loads and the available resistance. Also, the choice of input parameters requires revisiting. For example, a subsea mudmat supporting a pipeline end termination structure or manifold is subjected to episodic lateral loading from the thermal expansion and contraction of the attached pipelines and spools, causing associated biaxial moments and torsion depending on the attachment position of the pipelines and spools. When the same facility is decommissioned, this complex multi-directional loading (from pipeline operation) will cease, reducing (significantly) the loads transferred to the mudmat compared to during the operational design life. Instead, engineering assessments must quantify the risk of the facility being unstable and moving en masse or via dispersal to present a hazard to the environment or to other ocean users, e.g. shipping or nearby active facilities. A consequence of instability may simply be a requirement, after the instability has been identified via monitoring, that engineered stabilisation measures be introduced. Therefore, a different annual probability of failure may be tolerable post decommissioning and the engineering assessment may involve less onerous design events and reduced ‘safety factors’. As well as instability of the overall facility, it is necessary to consider the potential for disintegration and dispersion of the parts, and the associated hazards and impacts.

The contrasting contributions to the risk profile and actions (loads and resistance components) during operation and after in situ decommissioning are somewhat obvious, current engineering practices are not easily translated between scenarios. This is because of assumptions embedded in conventional design and a lack of previous focus on the very long term behaviour relevant to post-decommissioned integrity. As an example, most design codes specify partial factors on

loads and resistance that are predicated on the risk profile associated with an operating manned facility. These factors are sometimes derogated for a temporary or unmanned condition (e.g. via the safety classes adopted in some classification codes), but there is no specific approach yet established for decommissioned infrastructure.

As well as the differing design criteria and change in loading regime that apply before and after decommissioning, it is likely that the relevant material parameters will have altered, due to changes in the surrounding environment and the structural condition of the infrastructure over the previous tens of years of field operation. These changes can be positive or negative. The following section of this paper now focuses more closely on this topic, in relation to the whole-life changes in seabed strength around subsea infrastructure. The focus of this paper is geotechnical aspects of decommissioning. Whole-life behaviour of the structural materials is not considered.

6 Whole-life response of fine-grained seabeds around subsea infrastructure

6.1 Introduction

In this section the geotechnical response of fine-grained seabeds around subsea mudmats is considered as an example to illustrate potential challenges associated with retrieval, or the potential enhanced stability of subsea infrastructure at the end of field life if viewed through the lens of in situ decommissioning.

Uplift resistance, i.e. retrieval loads, for subsea infrastructure founded on or in fine grained seabeds can exceed the installed weight due to partial burial of the foundation, marine growth, and reverse end bearing developed under skirted mats (sustained by suction beneath the mat) during lifting, which depends on the strength of the seabed as well as the rate and duration of the loading.

Recent research aimed at quantifying reverse end bearing factors and whole-life seabed strength gains are presented in the following sections. These research outcomes demonstrate potential multi-directional capacity at the end of life, which can be viewed in terms of resistance that must be overcome for retrieval or a measure of stability for the afterlife of subsea structures left in situ after decommissioning.

6.2 Reverse end bearing capacity

Reverse end bearing resistance is provided by mobilisation of a zone of soil in undrained uplift similar to that mobilised under undrained vertical compression. This can significantly increase the uplift resistance of skirted shallow foundations compared to frictional resistance mobilised at the skirt-soil interfaces. Reverse end bearing is an attractive geotechnical phenomenon when considering operational capacity but presents a challenge when considering retrieval of a foundation.

Much research has been carried out to show that reverse end bearing can be relied on for undrained loading (Craig & Chua, 1990, Dyvik et al., 1993, Andersen et al., 1993, Watson et al., 2000, Craig et al., 2002, Acosta-Martinez et al., 2010, Mana et al., 2012, 2013a, Li et al., 2015) and further research has quantified appropriate undrained (reverse) bearing capacity factors for

shallow foundations (Martin & Randolph, 2001, Houlsby & Martin, 2003, Salgado et al., 2004, Edwards et al., 2005, Gourvenec & Mana, 2011, Feng et al., 2014). Physical modelling studies have shown equal bearing capacity factors for shallow skirted foundations in uplift and tension (e.g. Watson et al., 2000, Mana et al., 2012).

Figure 6 shows experimental evidence of reverse end bearing during undrained displacement-controlled uplift of a circular skirted foundation in lightly over consolidated clay. In this study, reverse end bearing capacity was shown to be of the same magnitude as compression capacity and was observed to be fully mobilised for skirt embedment ratios, d/D , as low as 0.1.

Figure 6: Experimental evidence of reverse end bearing during undrained uplift of shallow skirted foundations; (a) soil velocity vectors showing kinematic mechanism and (b) soil displacement contours from PIV analysis of centrifuge model tests, soil displacement normalised by applied foundation displacement (Mana et al., 2012)

Figure 7: Effect of skirt embedment ratio on undrained uplift resistance based on reverse end bearing and skirt-soil interface friction, for uniform s_u , $kD/s_{um} = kD/s_{u0} = 0$ (a) vertical bearing capacity factor and (b) ratio of resistance mobilised by reverse end bearing to skirt friction

Figure 7 compares the effect of skirt embedment ratio on uplift resistance based on mobilised reverse end bearing resistance and skirt-soil interface friction only. The reverse end bearing factors are taken from Gourvenec & Mana (2011). For the purpose of comparison, the skirt friction is normalised by the bearing area and undrained strength at skirt tip level (although is calculated based on surface area and average shear strength). Cases of a fully rough skirt-soil interface, $\alpha = 1$, providing an upper limit of uplift resistance, and intermediate interface roughness, $\alpha = 0.5$ are illustrated. The comparison in Figure 7a highlights the increased bearing capacity factor mobilised by reverse end bearing compared to skirt friction, and the more dominant effect of reducing interface roughness on skirt friction than reverse end bearing capacity. Note that in this example only peripheral skirts, not internal skirts, are considered. Figure 7b shows the ratio of uplift resistance mobilised through reverse end bearing to skirt friction, showing that a multiple-fold increase in uplift resistance will be experienced if reverse end bearing is mobilised, particularly for shallowly embedded mudmats.

Reverse end bearing uplift resistance under sustained loading diminishes with time due to seepage into the soil plug and softening of the soil. However, research shows that the timeframes for significant uplift displacement in fine grained material are impractical for retrieval of typical size subsea mudmats in clay soils (Gourvenec et al., 2009, Mana et al., 2013b, 2014, Li et al., 2013). Figure 8a shows the time-uplift displacement response of a circular skirted foundation with embedment ratio $d/D = 0.15$ in lightly over consolidated kaolin clay, under sustained uplift at proportions of the undrained vertical uplift capacity showing a relatively slow rate of uplift even at relatively high vertical loads. Figure 8b presents the same data as in Figure 8a (but for foundations with d/D of both 0.15 and 0.3) illustrating the required uplift load and duration to achieve various uplift displacements. Figure 8b indicates that it is impractical to rely on seepage to diminish uplift resistance for the purpose of retrieval - but shows that skirts provide valuable additional uplift and overturning capacity during the operational life over relatively long loading periods.

The kaolin clay in the tests of the results shown in Figure 8 had representative values of the coefficient of permeability $\sim 5E-10$ m/s and coefficient of consolidation $c_v \sim 2.6$ m²/year for the stress level at skirt tip; and foundation diameter $D = 20$ m (prototype scale). It is noted that negative excess pore pressures will dissipate more quickly in seabeds of higher permeability and lower drainage path length (or foundation size), but since time scales linearly with permeability and with drainage path length squared, significant increase in permeability or reduction in foundation size would be required for sustained loading to provide a practical approach to achieve reduced uplift resistance for retrieval of a subsea mudmat. The significance of reverse end bearing in the context of retrieval of subsea structures in fine grained seabeds has been reported by others (e.g. Small et al., 2015). Large break out forces have also been reported in porous seabeds if permeability is (relatively) low and loading rates are high (Jaek et al., 2008).

Mobilisation of reverse end bearing can be prevented if the top cap of the foundation is unsealed – via an open valve or vent – and drainage is provided across the foundation area, allowing flow of free water into the skirted compartment. In practice, foundations are often designed with sealable vents to maximise the availability of suction beneath the top cap to provide overturning uplift resistance while enabling vented installation. For retrieval, ideally valves in the top cap could and would be vented but there is no guarantee that the valve will still open, or that the foundation top cap could be vented in any other way and reliable drainage across the entire foundation area may difficult to assure.

Aside from the potential multiple-fold increase in bearing capacity factor from mobilisation of reverse end bearing, the operative strength is also likely to have increased over the life of the field due to consolidation under self-weight of the foundation and supported structure and operational loading. Consolidation strength gains are addressed in the subsequent sections.

Figure 8: Effect of sustained uplift on reverse end bearing capacity; circular skirted foundations in lightly over consolidated kaolin clay (a) uplift load-displacement relationship and (b) uplift load and duration for achieving pull out (Gourvenec et al., 2009)

6.3 Self-weight consolidation strength gains

Research has quantified gains in capacity of mat foundations due to changes in seabed strength due to consolidation under the self-weight of the foundation system and supported structure

(Bransby, 2002, Zdravkovic et al., 2003, Lehane & Gaudin, 2005; Gourvenec et al., 2014, Feng & Gourvenec, 2015, Vulpe et al., 2016a,b) and due to operational cycles of loading or movement (Cocjin et al., 2014, Cocjin et al., 2015, Feng & Gourvenec, 2016). In this section, increases in seabed strength and subsequent foundation capacity under vertical or multi-directional loading are considered. Strength and capacity gain due to operational cycles are considered in the following section.

Consolidation beneath a shallow foundation increases the shear strength of the seabed relative to the virgin in situ condition. The increase in strength and the zone of soil affected is non-uniform and dependent on the geometry of the foundation, relative load and degree of consolidation permitted. The change in shear strength of a normally consolidated deposit under vertical (self-weight) loading followed by full consolidation is illustrated in Figure 9 as contours showing the ratio of the consolidated undrained strength to the initial undrained shear strength in the virgin soil. A doubling of the initial undrained strength is achieved close to the underside of the foundation, decreasing with distance from the foundation.

Figure 9: Undrained strength gain due to self-weight loading from a shallow foundation after full consolidation (after Vulpe et al., 2016a)

The question is then, how to determine the operative shear strength that will govern foundation performance under the subsequent load path. This question is important whether considering loading during the life of the structure, required crane capacity for retrieval or stability of a foundation left in situ following the end of the operational life of a development.

This question has been addressed through a generalised critical state framework, in which gain in capacity is predicted as a function of preload by considering the affected soil as a single ‘lumped’ element (Gourvenec et al., 2014). The applied stress can be divided into elastic and plastic stress increments depending on the over consolidation ratio of the in situ soil. These stresses are then converted to an ‘operative’ preload defined by the applied preload scaled by a stress factor f_σ , to account for the non-uniform distribution of stress beneath the foundation (and to account for the vertical rather than mean stress being considered). The operative shear strength, $s_{u,op}$, can then be defined from the change in void ratio, Δe , under the operative preload, adjusted by a constant shear strength factor, f_{su} , to account for the non-uniform distribution of the increase in shear strength in the zone of soil that controls the consolidated capacity.

The basis of the framework is illustrated graphically in Figure 10. For normally consolidated conditions, in which all of the applied stress causes plastic compression of the foundation soil,

the gain in undrained vertical bearing capacity due to self-weight loading and full consolidation can be given by Equation 1.

$$\frac{V_{u,cons_max}}{V_u} = 1 + \frac{\Delta S_u}{S_u} = 1 + f_\sigma f_{su} R \left(\frac{V_p}{V_u} \right) N_{cv} \quad (1)$$

Where $V_{u,cons_max}$ is the maximum undrained vertical bearing capacity, i.e. after full consolidation; V_u is the unconsolidated undrained vertical bearing capacity factor; f_σ and f_{su} are the stress and strength factors as described above; R is the normally consolidated undrained strength ratio, s_u/σ'_v ; V_p is the applied preload (i.e. self-weight load) and N_{cv} is the vertical bearing capacity factor for undrained unconsolidated conditions. N_{cv} can be determined from either classical bearing capacity theory or from numerical and analytical solutions for various boundary conditions (e.g. Martin & Randolph, 2001, Houlsby & Martin, 2003, Salgado et al., 2004, Edwards et al., 2005, Gourvenec & Mana, 2011, Feng et al., 2014).

The study also showed that consolidated undrained capacity gain could be predicted through a hardening law, linking gain in capacity to settlement as a result of reduction in void ratio, as a linear function of the degree of consolidation, although this is of more relevance for foundation response during the operational life rather than at the end of the operational life, at which point the majority of consolidation would be expected to have occurred.

Figure 10: Critical state framework for consolidated strength gains (Gourvenec et al., 2014)

The separate stress and strength factors allow the response in over consolidated conditions to be captured, but for normally consolidated conditions there is effectively a single scaling parameter $f_\sigma f_{su}$ for a given load path and the form of Equation 1 can be used to predict consolidated undrained capacity under any uniaxial loading path (Feng & Gourvenec, 2016), as shown in Equation 2 and Figure 11. It was also shown that the combined load failure envelopes could be scaled by both relative preload and degree of consolidation (Figure 12). The increase in

multi-directional load capacity indicates enhanced resistance to sliding and overturning if left on the seabed post-decommissioning, as well as during the operational life.

$$\frac{H_{x(y)u,cons_max}}{H_{x(y)u}} = 1 + \frac{\Delta S_u}{S_u} = 1 + f_\sigma f_{su} R \left(\frac{V_p}{V_u} \right) N_{cv}$$

$$\frac{M_{xu,cons_max}}{M_{xu}} = 1 + \frac{\Delta S_u}{S_u} = 1 + f_\sigma f_{su} R \left(\frac{V_p}{V_u} \right) N_{cv}$$

$$\frac{M_{yu,cons_max}}{M_{yu}} = 1 + \frac{\Delta S_u}{S_u} = 1 + f_\sigma f_{su} R \left(\frac{V_p}{V_u} \right) N_{cv}$$

$$\frac{T_{zu,cons_max}}{T_{zu}} = 1 + \frac{\Delta S_u}{S_u} = 1 + f_\sigma f_{su} R \left(\frac{V_p}{V_u} \right) N_{cv}$$
(2)

Figure 11: Self-weight consolidation gain on undrained multi-directional capacity for normally consolidated deposit (Feng & Gourvenec, 2015)

Figure 12: Self-weight consolidation gain in undrained multi-directional capacity for normally consolidated deposit (a) as a function of relative pre-load and full consolidation and (b) as a function of degree of consolidation for a specific pre-load (Feng & Gourvenec, 2015)

6.4 Shearing, remoulding and reconsolidation from operational processes

Operational loading on a subsea mudmat derives predominantly from thermal expansion loads during heating and cooling of the attached pipelines during start up and shut down operations. In addition, there may be hydrodynamic loading from seabed currents. These loads occur episodically over the operational lifetime of the development, typically at rates to generate an undrained soil response during loading, and with sufficient rest periods between loading cycles to allow significant consolidation. This mode of episodic cyclic loading with intervening consolidation can lead to soil hardening, in contrast to the softening that is associated with undrained

cyclic loading of fine grained soil over shorter timeframes, such as during a storm event (Hodder et al., 2010, Cocjin et al., 2014, Feng & Gourvenec, 2016).

Figure 13: Schematic showing loading to a subsea mudmat during operation

Figure 14 shows the gain in lateral capacity of a shallow skirted square mudmat founded in normally consolidated kaolin clay, subjected to episodic horizontal loading with periods of intervening consolidation, from centrifuge modelling. The loads are shown normalised by the unconsolidated undrained horizontal capacity, H_{un} . Two initial tests were performed to identify this capacity, and also the capacity after consolidation under the self-weight of the foundation. This effect gave an almost doubling of the capacity, as marked on the left of Figure 14b. This is in good agreement with predictions from the theoretical framework outlined above (Gourvenec et al., 2014, Feng & Gourvenec, 2015). Having measured this capacity, an operating load was adopted as two-thirds of this capacity, and was applied for a total of 10 cycles each with intervening periods of consolidation, before the foundation was pushed to failure to measure the capacity enhancement. Different periods of consolidation were permitted between cycles and the greatest gains are related to the longer periods of intervening consolidation (as would be expected). Capacities of up to three times the initial horizontal capacity were observed (shown on the right of Figure 14b).

(a)

(b)

Figure 14: Episodic horizontal loading of a skirted mudmat (a) image of centrifuge model and (b) capacity for various loading patterns, including episodes of pre-failure horizontal loading and intervening consolidation

The results shown in Figure 14 involve episodic lateral loading of magnitude less than the ultimate limit state, such that the foundation remains essentially stationary. Recently, the traditional

paradigm that foundations for subsea infrastructure remain stationary has been challenged, with the notion of tolerably mobile foundations (Cathie et al., 2008, Cocjin et al., 2014, Cocjin et al., 2015, Deeks et al., 2014, Stuys et al., 2015). The design philosophy of a tolerably mobile mudmat is that it would slide across the seabed, tolerably, in response to the operational loads applied by the thermal expansion and contraction of the attached pipelines, rather than being designed sufficiently large to resist all the applied loading and remain stationary. Tolerably mobile foundations could then be designed with a smaller footprint, easing installation challenges of subsea mudmats as developments move into areas with softer seabeds, higher operational temperatures (due to deeper reservoirs) and heavier structures are required as more functions are carried out by the subsea structures that the foundations support (Gourvenec & Feng, 2014). An indication of a tolerably mobile subsea mudmat is illustrated schematically in Figure 15. During sliding, shear induced pore pressures are generated in the supporting seabed, which then dissipate while the foundation is stationary in the operational position.

Figure 15: Schematic representation of tolerably mobile subsea mudmat

Observations from centrifuge model tests of a sliding mudmat are shown in Figure 16 in terms of accumulated settlements with each cycle of sliding and dissipation of shear induced excess pore pressures, and the evolution of sliding resistance of the mudmat with increasing cycles of large amplitude lateral displacement and intervening consolidation. The tests modelled a whole-life scenario lasting over 70 years at prototype scale (Cocjin et al., 2014). It can be seen in both data sets that after a number of cycles of loading and consolidation, a steady state is reached at which there is no further propensity for generation of excess pore pressure and further reduction in void ratio. The observations from the centrifuge tests show that accumulated settlements are modest but gain in sliding resistance is significant – with a three-fold increase in sliding resistance after around 25 cycles of lateral loading and reconsolidation. Figure 16c shows the shear strength profile through the footprint of the foundation at the end of the test, carried out with a miniature T-bar penetrometer (Stewart & Randolph, 1994) showing an increase in the strength compared to the virgin state, to a depth of approximately $0.3B$ below the foundation.

It can be seen that the strength at the foundation-soil interface has increased significantly from shearing and reconsolidation, above the gain from self-weight preload.

Figure 16: Strength increase from consolidation (a) foundation settlement due to whole-life sliding with intervening consolidation (b) evolution of foundation sliding resistance with episodic sliding with intervening consolidation (after Cocjin et al., 2014) and (c) increase in shear strength profile in foundation footprint at end of life

Whole-life episodic lateral loading and consolidation response has been captured through a generalised critical state framework (Cocjin et al., 2016a). The framework has been validated against the centrifuge test results (illustrated in Figure 16) and is shown to capture the essential elements of the soil-structure interaction, which include (i) the changing soil strength from cycles of sliding and pore pressure generation, (ii) the regain in strength due to dissipation of excess pore pressure (consolidation), and (iii) the soil contraction and consequent settlement of the foundation caused by the consolidation process. The soil is idealised as a one-dimensional column of elements, each subject to a vertical total stress and cycles of horizontal shear stress, and responding according to a simple form of critical state model. The framework can be applied in a cycle-by-cycle manner, solving for the response at each soil element to determine the

6.5 Example case study: retrieval resistance or stability for the afterlife

A hypothetical scenario is considered here to illustrate the potential retrieval resistance at the end of operational life of a development - or the increased stability that can be expected for the afterlife of a foundation left in situ after decommissioning.

A rectangular subsea mudmat of width $B = 5$ m, width to length aspect ratio $B/L = 0.5$ and skirt embedment ratio $d/B = 0.2$, founded in a normally consolidated seabed with in situ undrained strength profile s_u (kPa) = $1 + 1.5z$ is considered.

Figure 18 shows the relative (submerged) self-weight of the foundation and structure, W' , as a proportion of the in situ undrained vertical bearing capacity in compression (that the foundation would have been designed against), plotted against the uplift resistance, V_{up} as a multiplier of the foundation self-weight W' . V_{up} defines the total uplift load required for retrieval, i.e. the sum of the geotechnical resistance and submerged weight of foundation, which would determine the crane lift requirement.

Uplift resistance based on A: self-weight only, and on self-weight and reverse end bearing based on B: the unconsolidated undrained shear strength, C: the consolidated undrained shear strength and D: the consolidated undrained shear strength following a whole-life sequence of lateral loading is shown in Figure 18. Full consolidation is considered since end of life assessment is being addressed. Vertical bearing capacity factors for the reverse end bearing calculations were taken from Feng et al., (2014), and the prediction of consolidated undrained vertical capacity was determined with the critical state theoretical framework presented in Gourvenec et al., (2014) with stress and strength factors for the foundation geometry considered taken from Feng and Gourvenec (2015). The vertical uplift resistance following whole-life episodic lateral loading was predicted from a single case numerical analysis, with an operative vertical load $0.3V_p/V_{uu}$. The dashed line passing through point D is indicative only.

Figure 18: Potential retrieval resistance, or stability for the afterlife, for a subsea mudmat at end of field life ($B = 5$ m, $B/L = 0.5$ and $d/B = 0.2$, s_u (kPa) = $1 + 1.5z$)

The predictions in Figure 18 show that for typical operating weights for subsea structures, retrieval loads may be 8 or 9 times higher than the weight of the foundation and structure at the end of life depending on the loading regime during operation. While capacity to weight ratios, such as plotted here as V_{up}/W' , are typical for defining efficiency of a foundation or anchoring system, in the context of retrieval, the measure becomes one of inefficiency.

Uplift resistance can be reduced by applying the uplift load eccentrically, although handling considerations may dictate that the lift is centric.

6.6 Summary

Research findings show that mobilisation of end bearing resistance and the increased seabed strength over the field life can have a significant impact on the required lift capacity for removal of subsea infrastructure; and a significantly higher lifting capacity may be required compared to installation. Viewed through the lens of in situ decommissioning, the research findings show that the geotechnical stability of subsea infrastructure may significantly increase over the field life. Gain in foundation capacity coupled with a reduction in loading on the infrastructure due to cessation of production (and therefore operational loads) and potentially partial removal, will tend to reduce the likelihood of the infrastructure being destabilised after decommissioning, relative to during the operating life.

7 Whole life response of mobile seabeds around pipeline infrastructure

A second example where emergent research provides evidence related to decommissioning options for subsea infrastructure is the study of pipeline stability on mobile seabeds. Offshore Australia, pipelines are generally laid directly on the seabed rather than being buried as is common practice in the North Sea, to avoid unwanted interaction with fishing gear. On-bottom pipelines must be designed to be adequately stable, and in conventional design practice, stability assessments neglect the mobility of the seabed. The analysis instead focusses on simulating fluid-pipe (drag, lift) and pipe-seabed (friction) effects without including the fluid-seabed interaction that leads to scour and erosion processes (e.g. Zeitoun et al., 2009). Stability assessments aim to show that during the most onerous storm event expected over the pipeline design life, the displacement of the pipe will not exceed some specified limit.

Observations from the field have shown that fluid-seabed interaction, leading to seabed mobility, can create significant changes in the embedment of pipelines and therefore their stability (Leuwenstein et al., 1985, Bruschi et al., 1997, Pinna et al., 2003, Bijker, & Chen 2001). These time-dependent changes often lead to an increase in stability of the pipe. This is relevant to both life extensions of the pipeline – which extend beyond the timeframe considered in the initial stability design – and also to any potential in situ decommissioning strategy. Emerging methods to predict these changes in embedment and assess the changing stability of the pipe offer a tool to assess the integrity and dispersion potential of pipelines that are decommissioned and left in situ, over the required future timescale.

Figure 19 shows the mechanisms of pipeline scour and sedimentation that cause changes in pipeline embedment. The first sub-figure describes scour and lowering (Figure 19a) and the second shows sedimentation (Figure 19b). Scour, sedimentation, or a combination of these

processes may occur when a pipeline is first placed on a seabed, causing changes in pipeline embedment. Scour is favoured where the pipeline embedment is low, and the seabed is undulating or the pipe has field joints of different diameter. Sedimentation is most common when suspended or bed load sediment transport occurs in the far field, transporting material that collects in the shear stress ‘shadows’ around the pipe (Zhao et al., 2015).

To observe these processes in controlled laboratory conditions, and replicate realistic near-sea-bed conditions found on Australia’s North West Shelf, a novel flume configuration, known as an O-tube, has been developed at the University of Western Australia (An et al., 2013). This flume comprises a horizontal fully enclosed circulating water channel, with a rectangular test section and an impeller-type pump driven by a motor. This arrangement has the advantages over conventional open-channel or U-tube flumes in that (i) currents can be introduced easily, and (ii) wave velocities are limited only by the pump characteristics and not by wave breaking, resonance of the water mass or the stroke of a piston.

Figure 19: Mechanisms of changing pipeline embedment: (a) scour leading to lowering, and (b) sedimentation. From Draper et al., (2016) and Leckie et al., (2015)

One of the first programs of research undertaken in the O-tube flumes provided support for the life extension process of the North West Shelf Venture’s First Trunkline (1TL) running from the North Rankin A platform to the Burrup Peninsula (Jas et al., 2012). This pipeline was originally installed in a trench, providing hydrodynamic shielding and additional soil resistance

(Figure 20a). However, subsequent cyclone activity had removed the trench and left the pipeline in a state of spatially-intermittent burial (Figure 20b). During a study performed to assess the condition of 1TL at the end of the original design life, it was identified that under conventional design codes it was not possible to demonstrate that the pipeline satisfied on-bottom stability requirements. However, it was recognised that potentially beneficial effects from seabed mobility could overcome this. To incorporate these effects in the design assessment, physical model testing was performed to provide additional information specific to the conditions relevant to this pipeline. These tests allowed the changing pipe embedment during the storm to be quantified. The resulting temporal variation in embedment and therefore hydrodynamic exposure and lateral pipe-soil resistance was used as input for 3D FE analyses of 1TL to assess the stability of the pipe under the current design storm. This method was effective in assessing the stability of 1TL, accounting for the mobile seabed environment (Jas et al. 2012).

Figure 20: Changing embedment of the 1TL trunkline between the North Rankin A platform and the Burrup Peninsula (a) typical as-built profile, (b) post cyclone Orson on-bottom profile (Jas et al., 2012)

The 1TL example was for a relatively light (gas-filled) large diameter pipeline. Smaller and heavier pipelines show an increased tendency to self-bury. Since this original study, systematic results from O-tube experiments representing a range of pipeline sizes and weights have been used to quantify the complex interactions shown in Figure 19. Ocean-pipeline-seabed interaction processes can be split into a series of 2D and 3D mechanisms. In two dimensions, the behaviour consists of (i) onset of scour, (ii) rate and limit of scour development, and (iii) backfilling. The three-dimensionality arises as scour propagates longitudinally along the pipeline from an initiation point, as well as vertically downwards. Also, an element of pipe will not drop directly into a scour hole as it opens. Instead, the pipe can self-bury through processes of sagging into a scour hole and sinking into span shoulders.

To validate these experimental observations, Leckie et al., (2015) studied remotely operated vehicle (ROV) survey video footage of other pipelines located on Australia's North West Shelf (NWS) (Figure 21). Video gathered at intervals over the life of the NWS pipeline network has been back-analysed, using the appropriate metocean and geotechnical data. This back-analysis work has involved the development of image analysis tools that allow reconstruction of the three-dimensional seabed topography from historic sonar profiler data (Leckie et al., 2016a). An example of the time-varying embedment of a pipeline on the NWS is shown in Figure 22, illustrating significant intermittent self-lowering over 4 years. The observed profiles of embedment were then used to assess the steady current required to cause the pipeline to breakout and become unstable. This analysis demonstrated a significant increase in pipeline

stability over that period (Figure 23, Leckie et al., 2016b). Other pipelines on the NWS have experienced sedimentation rather than scour, but this also resulted in an increase in stability (Leckie et al., 2016c). This study and other work (Mueller 2015) has identified that some of the seabed features around pipelines – including steep-sided trenches and conical sediment piles – were most probably created by fish.

Figure 21: Still images showing typical raw video footage and sonar data (Leckie et al., 2016a)

Figure 22: Temporal changes in the seabed topography around a pipeline on the NWS (Scale compressed in the along-pipe axis) (Leckie et al., 2015a)

Figure 23: Changes in the flow velocity, U_{crit} , required to cause pipeline instability through time, showing the increase in stability caused by seabed mobility (Leckie et al., 2016a). Each coloured line represents a different section of pipeline.

Work has been performed within the STABLEpipe Joint Industry Project supported by Woodside and Chevron to create more generic guidelines to allow seabed mobility to be considered in design (Draper et al., 2014). The general philosophy is to perform a two stage assessment. Firstly, the effect of seabed mobility is calculated to determine, through time, the spatial variation in embedment along the pipeline accounting for seabed mobility. Secondly, a conventional stability assessment is performed based on the assessed embedment profile. This approach is amenable to being extended to decommissioned pipelines. The long term pattern of changing embedment can be overlain on any changes in weight and stiffness as the pipeline deteriorates, allowing the long term integrity and dispersal potential to be estimated.

It is evident in Figure 20 that seabed pipelines on the North West Shelf represent a habitat for marine life. Other recent Australian observations of biota at oil and gas installations include Pradella et al., (2014) and Mueller (2015). If confidence in the long term pipeline stability and integrity of pipelines can be increased by quantifying the self-burial processes caused by seabed mobility, this helps to build a case for in situ decommissioning of pipelines, preserving their apparent ecological value.

8 Artificial reefs – infrastructure to augment the subsea habitat

If elements of an offshore installation will be left in situ, or moved to another location, where they will form an artificial reef that enhances the marine ecosystem, there is the possibility to engineer the most optimal enhancement. Artificial reefs have been installed at many nearshore locations offshore Australia, independent of offshore oil and gas infrastructure, and form a recreational resources for fishing or diving. These are generally formed of pre-fabricated units that are lowered to the seabed in a row or cluster. It has been proposed that such units could be used to augment relocated oil and gas infrastructure as part of in situ or relocated decommissioning options.

The engineering of an artificial reef unit is an interesting contrast to an oil and gas platform. The units are intended to provide shelter for an assemblage of fish of varying sizes, and promote

upwelling of nutrients from the sea floor by deviating the ocean flow. Typically they have a skeletal form with multiple openings and a central mast (Figure 24). The installation of the units should be simple, with minimal steps associated with founding or anchoring. A geotechnical site investigation is rarely performed, so the base should form a suitable foundation in any ground conditions that are encountered. In storm conditions, the reef is subjected to drag and lift forces, and should not topple although limited sliding may be permissible. There are similarities and differences with oil and gas platform requirements, and optimisation of this relatively new type of offshore structure requires partnership between the disciplines of engineering and ecology.

The Australian coast has many artificial reefs made from material of opportunity, such as sunken ships. More recently, custom-made artificial reefs have been installed, primarily to support recreational fishing. The Sydney offshore artificial reef was installed in 2011. It stands 12m high and features a steel frame tethered at each corner by concrete gravity anchors (Figure 24a). The artificial reef at Port Macquarie is composed of numerous reinforced concrete frames, each 5 m high (Figure 24b).

Figure 24. Artificial reefs: subsea structures for fish attraction and production (a) Schematic of Sydney offshore artificial reef (<http://www.famer.unsw.edu.au/research.html>) (b) Units used for Port Macquarie artificial reef (courtesy of Subcon Pty Ltd)

9 Final remarks

This paper has posed the question - from an engineering and ecological perspective is it more rational to leave offshore oil and gas infrastructure in situ after decommissioning? Both high level considerations acknowledging the multi-disciplinary nature of the decommissioning challenge, as well as specific recent geotechnical research that sheds light on some of the geotechnical aspects of decommissioning subsea structures have been presented.

The best solution to offshore decommissioning will depend on the scenario. No one solution will fit all cases, and the most appropriate solution will be influenced by for example, the development architecture and infrastructure, the nature of the offshore environment, ocean users and national or regional policy covering the area in which the infrastructure to be decommissioned is located. A growth in the evidence base will provide a more robust basis to select the appropriate decommissioning approach, and emergent knowhow and new technologies will increase the viability of all options – removal, relocation and leaving in situ.

An emergent theme from this work, and the broader activity related to decommissioning, is the potential positive benefits of full or partial in situ decommissioning. Combined efforts across engineering and marine science, coupled with suitable public awareness, policy and law, may lead to win-win outcomes across the relevant stakeholders, as we face the requirement to decommission much of the extensive infrastructure created by offshore production industries.

With appropriate coordination and collaboration, it is possible that these efforts will transform the physical legacy of abandoned offshore oil and gas projects from a liability on the private and public purse, to an asset within the marine ecosystem creating a beneficial increase or concentration of the ocean ecosystem, benefiting a diverse range of stakeholders.

What has been shown in this paper is that for subsea infrastructure it is generally more difficult to remove structures from the seabed than it was to place them and that the seabed may have transformed over the operational design life of the field to make subsea infrastructure more stable – through for example strengthening of the seabed or burial of infrastructure. When these whole-life enhancements of stability are viewed through the lens of in situ decommissioning, they become indicators of increased stability for a post-operational afterlife as part of the marine ecosystem.

These observations are geotechnical examples of the broader research across many disciplines that will provide an improved evidence base to support future policies and practices in decommissioning of both existing and future offshore infrastructure.

10 Acknowledgements

This work forms part of the activities of the Centre for Offshore Foundation Systems (COFS), supported as a node of the Australian Research Council's Centre of Excellence for Geotechnical Science and Engineering. The first author is supported by ARC grant CE110001009 and the second author is supported by the Shell EMI Chair in Offshore Engineering at UWA. This support is gratefully acknowledged.

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